

THE RELATIVE VAPOUR PRESSURE AND MOISTURE CONTENT OF ACTIVATED ALUMINA AND SILICA

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The moisture absorption capacity of a number of activated alumina, silica and ferric oxide samples prepared in different compounds has been studied. The materials were found to vary appreciably in their "Activity". Explanation has been offered for such differences.

Evidence is brought forth from these results regarding the mechanism of moisture absorption by alumina and silica in particular and by soils in general.

In comparatively recent years considerable literature has sprung up on the methods of preparation and utilisation of activated alumina and silica as absorbents for water and other vapours. It is believed that the vapours condense on the surface of these absorbents and are held in minute capillaries formed in the interstices between the alumina and silica particles. The pore size is determined by the size distribution of the particles formed during the precipitation of alumina and silica. The mode of preparation and subsequent treatments such as drying to different extents before washing, etc. have therefore a profound influence on material of this nature.

Among the earliest methods of preparing activated silica is that due to Patrick, Frazer and Rush (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 1511). Holmes and Anderson (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1925, 17, 280) prepared a porous silica gel by adding ferric chloride (instead of HCl) to sodium silicate solution, drying the gel so obtained to a moisture content of 55-60% and then removing the iron oxide from the firm solid by treating with acid. In the same way Holmes prepared other metallic oxide gels, *e. g.* alumina, calcium oxide, chromic oxide, copper oxide and nickel oxide, the oxides being removed as before. Although the same chemical compound, namely SiO_2 , was obtained in each case, the various samples had different adsorption capacity for different gases and vapours; furthermore, no single sample was found consistently to be the best adsorbent for all vapours. Holmes, Sullivan and Metcalf (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1926, 18, 386) in a later publication showed that the rate of drying had a decided influence on the quality of the product; the slower the rate, the better was the product. Holmes and Elder (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 82) found that an increase in the temperature of the acid treatment of the gel (in order to wash away the metallic oxides) from 30° to 100° increased its porosity.

A good deal of attention has also been paid to the preparation of activated alumina. The usual commercial product manufactured by the Aluminium Co. of America is prepared by dehydrating a crystalline hydrate which is a by-product of their process for the extraction of aluminium.

Adkins (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 2175) prepared activated alumina by the hydrolysis of aluminium methoxide, ethoxide, propoxide, isopropoxide and butoxide and used them for decarboxylation and dehydration purposes. Chowdhury

and Bagehi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 111) prepared alumina gel as a desulphurising agent in petroleum refining by precipitating aluminium hydroxide by the slow addition of ammonia under vigorous stirring to a solution of aluminium sulphate or aluminium chloride, the temperature not exceeding 25°. The gel was washed, dried in an air oven at 60-70° and activated by ignition. Perry (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1462) prepared alumina from aluminium sulphate by treating the latter with ammonia and studied its adsorption capacity towards various vapours after activating it by passing dry air heated to 200° over it.

The main difficulty about assessing the value of a particular preparation lies firstly in the fact that the mechanism of adsorption or activation is not fully understood, secondly there is no uniform standard of comparison. A good deal of light has been thrown on the mechanism of moisture absorption by soils by the recent work of Puri and co-workers (Puri and Crowther, *Pro. Roy. Soc.*, 1924, A, 106, 232). The evidence adduced is overwhelmingly in favour of the hypothesis that moisture is absorbed in the minute capillaries formed by the interstitial spaces between the particles. From the known relationship between the diameter of capillaries and the reduction in the vapour pressure of the water held in them, it is possible to calculate the size distribution of the capillaries as well as of the particles forming those capillaries. Moisture absorption from atmospheres of different humidities therefore affords an elegant method of comparing the absorption properties of activated silica and alumina.

In the present work, a number of alumina and silica gels was prepared by the various methods in vogue and then treated and activated in different ways. The size distribution of the pore spaces in the samples of alumina and silica was determined by studying their moisture absorption from atmospheres of different humidities. These observations, it was presumed, would give a measure of the activity of different samples.

EXPERIMENTAL

Moisture Absorption by Samples of Activated Alumina.

Preparation of the Material. (i) From Aluminium amalgam.—Alumina from aluminium amalgam was prepared in the manner described by Adkins (*loc. cit.*). The amalgam was prepared by covering fine strips of pure aluminium cut from thin sheets with ½% solution of mercuric chloride for 1½ minute and subsequent washing. After the completion of reaction between the amalgam and water, the precipitated alumina was collected on a filter paper, washed and then dried at 60-70° as recommended by Chowdhury and Bagehi (*loc. cit.*).

(ii) From Aluminium Nitrate.—The aluminium nitrate was calcined on an ordinary burner until no more red fumes were given out. The resulting pure white solid passed through a 200 mesh sieve with a little grinding and gave no test for nitrate.

(iii) *By Precipitation from AlCl_3 , $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$, Potash alum and Soda alum.*—Aluminium hydroxide was obtained in every case as a flocculent gelatinous precipitate by the slow addition of ammonia with vigorous stirring to the salt solution keeping the temperature below 25° , as Chowdhury and others (*loc. cit.*) have reported that higher temperatures yield comparatively poor absorbents. The precipitate in every case was washed free from impurities and was ultimately dried in an air oven at $60\text{--}70^\circ$.

The various samples of alumina were then activated at 200° in a stream of carbon dioxide for 2 hours.

Moisture Absorption by Activated Alumina at different Humidities.—Sulphuric acid—water mixtures corresponding to different humidities were prepared. About 2g. of the various samples, accurately weighed, were kept in crucibles and placed in vacuum desiccators containing the different sulphuric acid—water mixtures. The increase in weight of the samples was determined after two days as in preliminary experiments it was found that the maximum moisture absorption from atmosphere of a particular humidity takes place within this time.

Fig. 1.

Moisture absorption curves of activated alumina samples as compared with soil No. P. C. 13.

The results of moisture absorption by various samples of activated alumina at different humidities are given in Table I and plotted in Fig. 1.

TABLE I

Moisture absorption of various samples of alumina as compared with soil No. P. C. 13 from different humidities.

Alumina prepared from	% Moisture absorbed from different humidities					
	10%	50%	70%	90%	95%	99%
1. Al-amalgam	0.8	3.2	4.5	4.5	6.9	7.08
2. $Al_2(SO_4)_3$	7.1	14.05	16.1	23.9	53.5	62.0
3. $Al(NO_3)_3$	3.17	7.7	12.0	19.4	28.8	40.4
4. $AlCl_3$	11.1	12.5	15.6	21.6	48.0	57.3
5. Soda alum	6.9	7.5	11.1	12.3	19.1	19.1
6. Potash alum	6.2	6.2	10.7	12.0	15.8	18.9
Soil No. P. C. 13	4.81	9.33	11.78	...	16.8	19.57

It is seen that the samples of alumina prepared by precipitating from $AlCl_3$ and $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ absorb moisture to nearly the same extent at any given humidity. The alumina prepared by calcining $Al(NO_3)_3$ absorbs much less moisture from atmospheres of lower humidities but at higher humidities the moisture absorption increases though it does not equal the amount absorbed by the other two samples already referred to. This shows that most of the capillaries in this sample are of comparatively large size. This is probably due to the elimination of NO_2 gas during the calcination of $Al(NO_3)_3$. Continuous elimination of NO_2 and O_2 would leave larger gaps and spaces in between the molecules of alumina.

The samples prepared by precipitating from soda alum and potash alum absorb moisture nearly to the same extent as the one prepared from $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ at 10% humidity but with increase in humidity the difference in their moisture absorption capacity goes on increasing, the amount absorbed by the latter sample becoming ultimately far in excess of the others. This is because the elimination of K_2SO_4 and Na_2SO_4 from potash and sodium alums leaves behind much larger pore spaces which cannot effectively absorb moisture from the vapour phase. It is also worth noting that these two samples, prepared from alum, resemble each other in absorbing the same amount of moisture at all humidities. The sample prepared from aluminium amalgam absorbs very little moisture even from fully saturated atmosphere.

These results very clearly show that in the preparation of activated alumina, the method of preparation and the composition of the starting material are of great importance. Further, the total capillary space in an activated material is not the only consideration. In fact, the size of the capillaries is a much more important factor. The alumina prepared, for instance, from potash alum or by heating $Al(NO_3)_3$ will have larger capillary spaces on account of the elimination of larger molecules, but at the same time the size of the capillaries will be too big for effective moisture absorption from the vapour phase.

The moisture absorption curve for a soil sample at different humidities is also included in Fig. 1. The similarity between the soil and alumina curves is very striking. In both cases the curve between 10 and 70% humidity forms a straight line. The slope of this line seems to be characteristic for a particular type of the sample *i.e.*, it defines the hygroscopic nature of the material, just as in soils (Puri, *Soil Sci.*, 1932, 33, 405) and may be regarded as hygroscopicity of the sample from analogy with soils. Beyond 70% humidity the curves tend to become asymptotic. At humidities varying from 0 to 10% the curve has the least slope.

Absorption of Organic Vapours by the various Alumina Samples.—Evidence regarding the difference in capillary sizes of the various alumina samples was also obtained by determining their absorption of organic vapours. Holmes (*loc. cit.*) has shown that there is an optimum capillary size for each vapour to get absorbed. If this is so, the vapours of liquids with larger molecules will require correspondingly larger capillary spaces and *vice versa*. In other words the alumina prepared by heating $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ would absorb preferentially larger molecules and those prepared from AlCl_3 and $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ by precipitation would preferentially absorb smaller molecules. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Adsorption of organic vapours by different alumina samples (activated).

Alumina prepared from	Vapours absorbed (%)						
	Benzene.	Toluene.	Xylene.	CHCl_3 .	CCl_4 .	AcOCl .	Ph.COCl .
1. $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$	12.0	55.5	39.4	33.1	36.2	54.9	74.1
2. $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	3.5	17.9	15.6	15.0	13.0	19.9	38.5
Ratio : % vapour adsorbed by 1 to % of that absorbed by 2.	0.29	0.32	0.39	0.45	0.36	0.36	0.52

It is seen that as the size of the molecule increases, the ratio of vapour adsorbed by alumina prepared from aluminium nitrate to that adsorbed by the one prepared from $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ goes on increasing.

Titration Curves of Alumina Samples.—Three samples of alumina namely those prepared (i) by calcining $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, (ii) by precipitating from aluminium amalgam, and (iii) by precipitating from $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ were selected. To 0.1 g. portions of these samples increasing amounts of $N/10\text{-NaOH}$ or HCl were added and the total volume was made 10 c.c. by the addition of water. The pH values were taken after shaking the suspensions for 48 hours. The results are plotted in Fig. 2.

It is seen that the buffer capacity of the alumina prepared from $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ is the greatest both towards acid and alkali and that of the alumina prepared from the amalgam is the least. This is in accordance with the moisture absorption observa-

Fig. 2.

Titration curves for activated alumina samples with HCl and NaOH.

tions of these samples recorded in Table I and discussed before. It is a remarkable fact that although in each case we are dealing with the same chemical compound, yet in each case it has different quantity of acidity as well as alkalinity.

Moisture Absorption by Activated Silica Samples prepared by different Methods.

Silica samples were prepared by various methods and their moisture absorption capacities at different humidities were compared.

The actual methods used in the preparation of these materials are outlined below :

1. *Patrick's Method.*—The silica was obtained by mixing with continuous stirring a hot solution (50°) of HCl containing 10% by weight of the gas with an equal volume of sodium silicate solution of density 1.185. The mixture set to a gel in about an hour's time. It was then broken up into small lumps and washed free from salts, etc and then allowed to dry slowly at the room temperature. The dried lumps were ground to pass 200 mesh, and then activated.

2. *Holme's Method.*—Five samples of silica were obtained by this method. They were prepared from mixtures of different metallic oxide-silica gels, precipitated in the first instance by the addition of different salt solutions to solutions of sodium silicate. Ferric oxide-silica gel mixture, for instance, was formed by slow addition with violent stirring of 2 litres of 2*N*-FeCl₃ solution to 625 c.c of sodium silicate solution (sp. gravity, 1.375) which had previously been diluted with 12.5 litres of water. The mixture was allowed to stand for 60 hours and then filtered through

a fine muslin. The gelatinous mass was allowed to stand in a layer about 5 cm. deep for a few days till it could be handled, and was then broken up into uniform lumps about 2 cm. in diameter. When the water content of the lumps fell to about 50-60%, which required nearly a fortnight, the whole mass was kept in a bottle to prevent evaporation and allowed to "sweat" for a week. The mass consisting of the hydrous oxides of both iron and silicon was then subjected to steam for one hour and then heated to 80° with 9*N*-H₂SO₄, a process which dissolved the iron oxide. Repeated washings were then made to remove the iron and excess acid, after which the gel was dried at approximately 150° for 8 hours. It was then reduced to 200 mesh and activated.

In a similar way gel containing oxides of chromium, copper, cobalt and nickel, mixed with silica were prepared by adding 500 c.c. of 0.22*N* solutions of the metallic chlorides to 50 c.c. of water glass solutions (*d*, 1.375) diluted to one litre. The gels were then dried, steamed, treated with acid, washed, dried and activated just as described above.

3. *Bartel and Fue's Method.*—A high grade of water glass was diluted to a sp. gravity of 1.025 and neutralised with 1 : 1 HCl (Bartel and Almy, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 475). Before the mixture had set to a gel, saturated nickel nitrate solution was added in the proportion of 200 c.c. nickel nitrate to 1000 c.c. of silicic acid solution. The mixture very soon set to a solid green gel and was allowed to synerize at 90°, till the gel seemed to be thoroughly dried. It was then washed with dilute HCl, until the filtrate no longer gave test for Ni with dimethyl glyoxime. It was then heated at 250° in a beaker for two hours, and poured immediately after in cold distilled water. This last treatment, which was repeated several times, caused larger granules to split apart and aided in removing the remaining traces of HCl. The gel was finally dried at 200° and then powdered to 200 mesh and activated.

4. *Silica precipitated by the addition of Ammonium Salts.*—1 Lb. of sodium silicate solution of sp. gravity 1.2 was diluted with equal volume of water and to this 0.8735 equivalent of the ammonium salt, dissolved in 3 litres of water, was added. The resulting gel was broken up into small lumps of 2" size, after it had set for 24 hours, and washed with hot water to remove ammonium salts.

Seven samples of silica were obtained by this method, using NH₄Cl, (NH₄)₂SO₄, NH₄NO₃, (NH₄)₂CO₃, (NH₄)₂CrO₄, CH₃COONH₄, and ammonium tartrate, as precipitants.

5. *Silica from fused Sodium Silicate.*—Fused sodium silicate (20g.) was boiled with 450 c.c. of 8*N*-H₂SO₄ for two hours and after washing, the precipitate was dried at 150° and then activated.

Activation of Silica Samples.—The usual method of activating silica consists in passing air continuously over the sample heated to 200° for about 2 hours. It was thought of interest to activate some of the samples by passing CO₂, instead of air, and to compare the activity of air-activated and CO₂-activated samples with each other. The results of these experiments are given in Table III

TABLE III
*Comparison of moisture absorption by silica samples
 activated in air or CO₂.*

Silica prepared by	Moisture absorption (%) at humidities					
	10%	50%	70%	90%	95%	98.7%
1. Bartel & Fua method						
Air activated	13.9	15.0	23.2	43.1	71.0	80.0
CO ₂ "	20.8	26.0	27.2	48.8	74.0	90.0
2. Patrick gel						
Air activated	23.7	23.7	34.7	42.6	59.0	59.0
CO ₂ "	30.2	30.2	34.6	45.0	64.5	66.5
3. Silica prepared from fused sodium silicate.						
CO ₂ activated.	12.0	13.9	15.5	21.7	38.1	38.1
Air activated.	5.6	5.6	5.6	9.5	33.1	33.1

It is seen that CO₂-activated samples absorb more moisture than the air activated ones practically at all humidities. It appears that passage of CO₂ over heated silica is more effective in the removal of residual moisture during the process of activation than air. Activation in CO₂ therefore appears to be an advantage and for this reason the rest of the samples were activated in CO₂ only.

Moisture Absorption of Activated Silica at various Humidities.—Various samples of silica, activated in CO₂, were then taken and their moisture absorption curves determined by noting the increase in weight produced when they were kept over atmospheres of different humidities. The results are given in Table IV and plotted in Fig. 3.

TABLE IV
*Moisture absorption by various activated silica samples
 prepared in different ways.*

Description of the samples.	Absorption of moisture (%) at humidities					
	10%	50%	70%	90%	95%	99%
1. Patrick's gel	30.2	30.2	34.6	45.0	64.5	66.5
2. Holmes' gel obtained by mixing sodium silicate solution with —						
a. FeCl ₃	6.6	38.2	39.8	41.0	65.8	72.2
b. Chromium chloride	6.3	28.4	28.4	62.6	62.6	67.4
c. Cobalt chloride	5.9	35.8	38.0	63.6	64.4	70.4
d. Nickel chloride	5.8	36.5	38.0	50.8	71.6	86.3
3. Bartel and Fua gel	20.8	26.0	27.2	48.8	74.0	90.0
4. From fused sod. silicate	12.0	13.9	15.5	21.7	38.1	38.1
5. NH ₄ Cl + sod. silicate	3.8	4.9	11.4	12.6	52.8	54.4
6. (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ + "	5.5	5.9	17.6	69.6	69.6	71.0
7. NH ₄ NO ₃ + "	5.4	8.5	16.1	52.1	52.1	52.1
8. Amm. carbonate + "	3.7	10.9	14.5	46.0	46.0	51.3
9. Amm. oxalate + "	3.5	5.6	16.8	52.0	53.0	58.0
10. Amm. tartrate + "	5.2	8.2	15.5	54.4	54.6	57.3
11. Amm. chromate + "	1.0	3.6	18.5	40.2	40.2	43.0

These results give a clear concept of the comparative size of the capillary spaces of the various samples. At low humidities Patrick's silica gives the maximum moisture absorption. The various types of Holme's silica, as these are prepared from different metallic oxide-silica gels after dissolution of the metallic oxides, have wider capillaries and therefore absorb more moisture from atmospheres of higher humidities. At about 70% humidity the curves for these samples cross the curve for Patrick's silica gel (Fig. 3) and at all humidities lower than 70% Patrick's silica gel absorbs more moisture than do Holme's samples and at all humidities

Fig. 3.
Moisture absorption curves of activated silica gels prepared by diff. methods

higher than 70% Holmes' samples are better adsorbents. In this connection it may be mentioned that Holmes and his co-workers claim better adsorption capacity for their samples. This is because they determined adsorption of benzene and other organic vapours from fully saturated atmospheres and concluded that their samples were superior to the Patrick's sample. The dissolution of metallic oxides from metallic oxide-silica gel, originally prepared by Holmes method, would no doubt leave the resulting silica more porous, but it also results in widening the capillaries and thus making the samples poor adsorbents of moisture and other vapours from atmospheres of lower vapour pressure. Patrick's silica, in fact, is superior to Holmes' samples, if absorption is to take place from atmosphere of lower vapour pressures and the claim of Holmes, *etc.* that their sample is a better adsorbent is true only when absorption is to take place from saturated or nearly saturated atmospheres. It is also clear that Patrick's silica as an efficient drying agent

is superior to that of Holmes, but the latter is more effective if only partial drying is aimed at.

Bartel and Fue's silica also compares favourably with Holmes' silica obtained from nickel oxide-silica gel with which it resembles in the method of preparation, as it absorbs comparatively much moisture at all humidities excepting 50 to 70%.

The silica sample prepared by treating fused sodium silicate with H_2SO_4 is seen to be a poor absorbent at all humidities except at 10%.

The similarity in moisture absorption of the various forms of silica prepared by the addition of ammonium salt solutions to sodium silicate solution is striking and is just to be expected, since in each case the precipitation of silica involves the same chemical reaction. At lower humidities they absorb very little moisture but with increase in humidity the moisture absorption increases and the values at higher humidities are nearer although at no point they become equal to those for Holme's and Patrick's samples. It appears that liberation of ammonia gas from the unstable ammonium silicate first formed, leads to widening of the capillaries and thus lowering of their moisture absorption capacity from the vapour phase at low humidities.

Effect of Grinding on the Activity of Silica Samples.—Two samples of silica were prepared by precipitating them from sodium silicate by the addition of NH_4NO_3 and $(NH_4)_2SO_4$. In each case one portion of the sample was ground to pass through 200 mesh and another portion was not ground at all but was activated in the form of lumps, each lump being nearly 5 mm. in diameter. The results are given in Table V.

TABLE V

Effect of powdering on the moisture absorption properties of silica.

Silica prepared from	Moisture absorption (%) at different humidities					
	10%	50%	70%	90%	96%	99%
1. Am sulphate + sodium silicate						
Lumps	5.5	8.9	17.8	69.6	69.6	71.0
Powder	3.8	8.3	15.7	59.8	59.8	59.8
2. Am. nitrate + sodium silicate.						
Lumps	10.0	13.2	23.4	61.7	61.7	61.7
Powder	5.4	8.5	16.1	52.1	52.1	52.1

The results show that lumps possess slightly better absorption capacity at all humidities. This shows that unless it is required for some particular purpose the silica need not or, in fact, should not be powdered, as it results in a slight decrease in its moisture absorption capacity. Grinding, it appears, breaks down some of the finer capillary walls thereby adversely affecting its vapour absorption property.

These results also reveal incidentally that water absorbed by silica, or at least a considerable portion of it, is not due to any chemical combination between silica and water, *i. e.* water is not absorbed as water of hydration, because, if that were so, moisture absorption in either case of lumps or powdered form should have been the same, or perhaps even slightly more so in the case of the powdered sample on account of comparatively large surface exposed by it. It appears, therefore, quite certain that almost entire amount of moisture absorbed by silica is held in its capillary micropores.

Moisture Absorption of Ferro-alumino Silicates before and after Activation.

Ferro-alumino silicates, prepared by the addition of mixtures of ferric and aluminium chlorides solution to sodium silicate solution have been shown to be allied to soils in various physico-chemical properties including moisture absorption at various humidities (Puri, Balwant Rai and Verma, *Soil Sci.*, 1944, 58, 209). Holmes prepared $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{SiO}_2$ gel by a similar method, namely by the addition of ferric chloride to sodium silicate solution and showed it to be better adsorbent than Patriok's silica gel, and found further that dissolution of ferric oxide by acid left behind a still better adsorbent SiO_2 gel.

The results of moisture absorption of activated and unactivated ferro-alumino silicates of different composition are given in Table VI and they clearly show that activation is a distinct advantage.

TABLE VI
*Moisture absorption of ferro-alumino silicates
at different humidities*

Composition. Sample No.	Humidities					
	10%	50%	70%	90%	95%	100%
1. Iron silicates						
a. unactivated	1.6	6.0	12.4	18.8	31.2	34.7
b. activated	6.8	8.8	14.2	20.5	30.2	32.8
2. Fe silicate 80% + Al silicate 20%						
a. unactivated	0.0	0.0	3.0	17.0	23.0	26.0
b. activated	8.2	10.2	18.02	26.4	30.8	40.0
3. Fe silicate 50% + Al silicate 50%						
a. unactivated	—	—	—	—	—	—
b. activated	11.05	13.0	20.5	27.5	30.2	43.5
4. Fe silicate 40% + Al silicate 60%						
a. unactivated	—	—	—	—	—	—
b. activated	10.5	18.6	24.2	27.5	41.2	43.2
5. Fe silicate 20% Al silicate 80%						
a. unactivated	0.8	8.8	13.0	21.9	32.6	32.0
b. activated	12.5	17.4	27.0	38.0	49.5	44.0
6. Holmes silica prepared by dissolution of Fe_2O_3 activated.	6.6	38.2	39.8	44.0	65.8	72.2

In this table are also included the data obtained with Holmes silica prepared from ferric oxide-silica gel. It is seen that at 10% humidity, iron oxide-silica gel (sample No. 1) absorbs more moisture; but at all higher humidities, the silica gel, obtained after dissolution of ferric oxide, absorbs more moisture. This is because, as a result of dissolution of iron oxide, more capillary space becomes available with simultaneous increase in the size of the capillaries.

The results given in Table VI further show that as the percentage of alumina increases, the moisture absorption goes on increasing at almost all humidities. This is probably due to the fact that alumina is a better absorbent than ferric oxide. This point was tested by comparing moisture absorption of ferric oxide and alumina samples prepared and activated in similar manner. For this purpose two samples of ferric oxide and alumina were precipitated from their chlorides and sulphates by the addition of ammonia. They were subsequently washed, dried and then activated. The results of moisture absorption are given in Table VII. It is seen that Al_2O_3 is a better absorbent at all humidities.

TABLE VII

*Comparison of moisture absorption capacity
of $Fe(OH)_3$ and $Al(OH)_3$, both activated.*

	Moisture absorbed (%) from atmosphere of different humidities.					
	10%	50%	70%	90%	95%	99%
1. a. $Fe(OH)_3$ obtained from Ferric sulphate	6.1	6.1	12.1	13.7	15.6	17.1
b. Alumina obtained from $Al_2(SO_4)_3$	7.1	14.05	16.1	23.9	63.5	62.0
2. a. $Fe(OH)_3$ obtained from ferric chloride.	8.1	8.2	13.5	15.7	24.0	25.4
b. $Al(OH)_3$ obtained from $AlCl_3$.	11.1	12.5	15.6	21.6	48.0	57.3

The results mentioned in the foregoing clearly show that all the three main constituents of soils, namely Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 and SiO_2 , are good absorbent on account of their cellular nature and this leaves no doubt that moisture absorption and its retention in soils is due, in a large measure, to the presence of these substances. The mechanism of moisture absorption appears to be that it is held up in the capillary spaces between the individual molecules or aggregates of Fe_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 . The partial elimination of the sesquioxides from soils on treatment with acids, results in widening the capillary spaces, making the material good adsorbent for the purpose of bleaching crude vegetable oils and other allied purposes, but at the same time decreasing its moisture absorption capacity from the vapour phase.

Bleaching of Vegetable Oils by Silica Samples.

It was thought of interest to study the bleaching properties of various silica samples towards crude vegetable oils. Crude cotton seed oil was selected for this purpose. The method employed was the same as used by Sarin and Kukeraja (*J. Indian Chem. Soc. Ind. & News Ed.*, 1941, 4, 184) and consisted in mixing 0.5 g. of silica with 10 c.c of the crude oil and heating the mixture at 90° for 10 minutes with constant stirring. The oil was then filtered and the extent of bleaching determined by means of the Duboscq colorimeter taking the unbleached oil as the standard. The results are given in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII

Bleaching of oils by different activated silica samples.

No.	Description of sample.	Bleaching values :	
		Liquid depths giving the same colour as 10 depths of original oil values for	
		activated samples.	unactivated samples.
A.	Silica sample obtained by method of Bartel and Fue.	13.7	12.55
B.	Patrick gel.	13.6	11.8
C.	Holmes silica obtained by mixing		
1.	CrCl ₃ +sod. silicate solution.	12.0	11.6
2.	Ni chloride+sod. silicate solution	14.00	12.55
3.	Co chloride + sod. silicate solution.	13.00	12.9
4.	Ferric chloride+sod. silicate solution.	15.5	14.0
D.	Silica obtained by boiling fused sodium silicate with sulphuric acid.	11.43	
F.	Bleached.	17.2	
G.	Tonsil	15.8	

Similar results obtained with bleached and tonsil, two commercial bleaching materials used for this purpose, are also included in the table. It is seen that activated samples of silica are fairly good adsorbents for colouring matters and that the sample prepared from ferric oxide-silica gel (No. C. 4) gives the best results.

Effect of Time of Activation on Moisture Absorption capacity of Silica Samples.

On perusal of literature it is found that usually two hours of activation is recommended. During this time it is presumed that the maximum drying of the capillaries has taken place. The effect of temperature at which activation is done has been studied in details by Holmes and Elder (*loc. cit.*) who found that heating to a temperature anywhere between 100° and 800° does not affect the quality of the sample. Heating beyond 800°, however, was found to decrease the activity appreciably. Usually activation is done therefore at 200°. The effect of time of activation has not been studied in details so far. It was therefore thought of interest to activate the sample for different lengths of time and to study any change produced in the activity of the sample. Results of these experiments are given in Table IX. It is seen that moisture absorption capacity of the sample at all humidities goes on increasing with increase in the time of activation up to three hours. If activation is continued for a longer time, it seems that while little or no change is produced as far as moisture absorption from atmospheres of higher humidities are concerned, there is a fall in the values obtained from atmospheres of lower humidities (up to 50%).

TABLE IX

Moisture absorption capacity as affected by the time of activation.

Time.	10%	50%	70%	90%	98%	99%
1 hr.	7.0	8.8	16.3	34.1	63.4	70.1
2	14.0	14.5	19.6	36.0	73.4	74.2
3	16.4	18.4	22.4	38.8	70.0	75.8
5	12.3	12.6	23.5	39.0	68.0	74.6
7	12.5	13.3	23.5	39.2	68.5	75.2
9	11.2	11.8	21.8	36.8	69.7	75.8

It appears therefore that the period of activation should not exceed 3 hours. During this time most of the water present in the unactivated sample is removed. The rest of the water seems to be held much more firmly, apparently in such fine capillaries that when this water is sought to be removed either by increasing the time of activation, or by raising the temperature, the gel structure appears to partially collapse, decreasing its moisture absorption capacity.